

Recent results from the SND@LHC experiment

NuPhys2026: Prospects in Neutrino Physics

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Jan 8, 2026

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FEDERICO II

The SND@LHC experiment

Recent results

Detector upgrade and summary

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The SND@LHC experiment

Scattering and Neutrino Detector at the LHC (SND@LHC), experiment located 480 m from the ATLAS interaction point, slightly off-axis $7.2 < \eta < 8.4$

Shielded by $\simeq 100$ m of rock and LHC magnets which deflect charged particles

Study of $pp \rightarrow \nu X$ in unexplored energy range 300 GeV – few TeV

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Physics potential of an experiment using LHC neutrinos

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Published 11 October 2019 • © 2019 IOP Publishing Ltd

[Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics, Volume 46, Number 13](#)

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Further studies on the physics potential of an experiment using LHC neutrinos

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Published 4 November 2020 • © 2020 The Author(s). Published by IOP Publishing Ltd

[Journal of Physics G: Nuclear and Particle Physics, Volume 47, Number 12](#)

Phys. Rev. Lett. 122, 041101
(2019)

The SND@LHC physics program

Neutrino interactions

- ▶ Measure ν interactions in new TeV energy range
- ▶ Large yield of ν_τ will likely double existing data of 20 events by DONuT and OPERA
- ▶ Detection of all three types of neutrinos allows for tests of lepton flavour universality

QCD

- ▶ Decays of charm hadrons contribute significantly to the neutrino flux in SND@LHC \rightarrow probe of charm quark production in a forward region

Beyond the Standard Model

- ▶ Search for new feebly interacting particles (FIPs) decaying within the detector or scattering off the target

Flavour	DIS-CC	DIS-NC
$\nu_\mu + \bar{\nu}_\mu$	1270	410
$\nu_e + \bar{\nu}_e$	390	130
$\nu_\tau + \bar{\nu}_\tau$	30	15
Tot	1690	555

Expected neutrino interactions in RUN3: 250 fb⁻¹

Tech. proposal LHCC-P-016
JINST 19 P05067 (2024)

The SND@LHC detector

Veto system

- ▶ 2 (2022–2023) / 3 (2024–) 1 cm thick scintillator planes

Target, vertex detector and electronic calorimeter

- ▶ 830 kg tungsten target, $84X_0$ and $3 \lambda_{\text{int}}$
- ▶ Five walls \times 59 emulsion layers + five scintillating fibre stations

Hadronic calorimeter (HCAL) and downstream muon system (DS)

- ▶ Eight 20 cm Fe blocks + scintillator planes ($9.5 \lambda_{\text{int}}$).
- ▶ Last 3 planes (DS) have finer granularity to track outgoing muons.

JINST 19 P05067 (2024)

Event reconstruction

Electronic detectors

- ▶ Identify signal candidates (ν or FIPs)
- ▶ Identify muon candidates (with SciFi and Muon System)
- ▶ Energy measurement (with SciFi and Muon System)

Nuclear emulsions

- ▶ Extract and analyze emulsion data
- ▶ Reconstruct ν primary and secondary vertices
- ▶ Match emulsion and electronics reconstruction (timestamp and energy measurement)

Discriminate between $\nu_{e,\mu,\tau}$ flavors

Detector operations

Electronic detectors (curves)

- ▶ Recorded over 300 fb^{-1} with 97 % uptime
- ▶ 2022+2023 data used in analyses so far is around 20 % of the total

Emulsions (boxes)

- ▶ 20 emulsion targets ($\sim 215 \text{ m}^2$) exposed and developed in 2022–2025
- ▶ 264 fb^{-1} integrated.

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Muon flux measurement

Crucial for detector operations and physics analyses.

- ▶ Main backgrounds are muon induced
- ▶ Measurement of muon flux with 2022 data (Eur. Phys. J. C 84, 90 (2024))
 - ▶ Excellent agreement between subdetectors, including emulsions
 - ▶ Agreement with MC predictions within 20 %
- ▶ Measurement of muon flux in heavy ions collisions
 - ▶ Allows for further validation of the background under different physics conditions
 - ▶ Cross-check of detector performance

Observation of ν_μ with electronic detectors

High purity sample of ν_μ CC events in 2022 data: Phys. Rev. Lett. 131, 031802 (2023)

- ▶ Neutral vertex event (start in target walls 3 or 4)
- ▶ Large hadronic activity in the SciFi and HCAL
- ▶ Isolated outgoing muon track reconstructed DS
- ▶ Hit time consistent with event originating from IP1
- ▶ 8 candidate events, background 0.086, significance 6.8σ
- ▶ Updated results with with more data and improved analysis in preparation!

Candidate event in data

Observation of 0μ events in SND@LHC

Measurement using electronic detectors, sensitive to ν_e or ν_τ CC, and NC interactions. First observation of non- ν_μ CC neutrino interaction using electronic detectors at the LHC. First step towards flavour classification with SND@LHC.

9 candidate events, background of 0.32, observation with significance 6.4σ

Muon trident cross-section measurement

SND@LHC is sensitive to muon trident interactions ($\mu^\pm + N \rightarrow \mu^+ \mu^- \mu^\pm + N$) produced in the rock upstream. Cross-section measurement in progress.

[arXiv:2510.18943](https://arxiv.org/abs/2510.18943)

Emulsion scanning and analysis

Emulsion scanning is performed with fully automated microscopes in six laboratories: CERN, Bologna, Napoli, Nagoya, Gran Sasso and Santiago.

Maximum track density of 4×10^5 tracks/cm² (factor 10^3 larger than OPERA)

Achieved emulsion track position resolution < 150 nm.

Scanned emulsion data: $800 \text{ kg} \times 53 \text{ fb}^{-1}$

Reconstructed emulsion data: $40 \text{ kg} \times 70 \text{ fb}^{-1}$

Position resolution

Angular resolution

Electromagnetic shower measurement in emulsion

Electromagnetic shower identification is fundamental for ν_e detection

- ▶ Reconstruct tracks inside a cylinder
- ▶ Energy estimate based on the number of tracks at shower maximum

Momentum measurement in emulsion

Momentum of particles can be measured in emulsions using multiple Coulomb scattering

Estimated resolution on simulated charged pions 15–25 %.

Neutrino energy resolution for simulated vertices $\simeq 20\%$.

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SND@LHC upgrade for HL-LHC

Extending neutrino physics measurements at the TeV scale with increased statistics offered by HL-LHC. **Approved for Run 4!**

- ▶ Same location of SND@LHC, TI18
- ▶ Emulsions replaced with silicon detector, 30 μm resolution expected.
- ▶ Magnetised calorimeter is foreseen \rightarrow measurements of muon momentum and charge $\rightarrow \nu/\bar{\nu}$ discrimination.

Measurement	Run 3		Run 4	
	Uncertainty Stat.	Uncertainty Sys.	Uncertainty Stat.	Uncertainty Sys.
Gluon PDF ($x < 10^{-5}$)	5%	35%	2%	5%
ν_e/ν_τ ratio for LFU test	30%	22%	6%	10%
ν_e/ν_μ ratio for LFU test	10%	10%	2%	5%
Charm-tagged ν_e/ν_μ ratio for LFU test	-	-	10%	< 5%
ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$ cross-section	-	-	1%	5%

SND@HL-LHC technical proposal (LHCC-P-026)

Summary

SND@LHC is a ν experiment at CERN, operating since the start of LHC Run 3.

- ▶ Designed to measure high-energy neutrinos at the LHC, it can study lepton universality in the neutrino sector, probe heavy-flavour physics, and search for BSM signatures.
- ▶ Has recorded $\simeq 300 \text{ fb}^{-1}$ of data, with 97% detector uptime

Published results

- ▶ ν_μ , μ flux, first observation of 0μ LHC neutrino interactions using electronic detectors

Upcoming results

- ▶ Updated ν_μ measurement, μ -trident cross-section, calorimetric measurements with emulsions using multiple Coulomb scattering and shower track density

Detector upgrade

- ▶ Approved for Run 4. Silicon strip modules in place of nuclear emulsion to cope with the high-intensity of the HL-LHC, and magnetised volume for $\nu/\bar{\nu}$ discrimination

Thank you for listening!